

Literature Review on Brain Activity, Muscular Activity, Cardiovascular Activity, and Movement Dynamics as Candidate Physical Fatigue Indicators

Brain Activity

Given that the brain largely initiates muscle movement, brain activity can be an indicator of physical fatigue (Loizaga et al., 2023). Concretely, M. Tanaka et al. (2013) report that muscular fatigue leads to an alignment of neuronal positive–negative directions in the posterior cingulate cortex, resulting in the formation of equivalent current dipoles (ECDs). In addition, reductions in peak alpha frequency (PAF) in both the frontal and prefrontal cortex regions (Damit et al., 2017), as well as in areas surrounding the motor cortex have been observed as a result of fatigue (Ng & Raveendran, 2007).

Brain activity is typically measured via electroencephalography (EEG) or magnetoencephalography (MEG) (Loizaga et al., 2023; Tanaka et al., 2013). However, as can be seen from Figure 1, EEG and MEG require dedicated equipment positioned around the operator's head. Therefore, they are intrusive measurement techniques (Cavuoto & Megahed, 2017; Loizaga et al., 2023). For these reasons, brain activity is excluded as a physical fatigue metric in this study, and EEG and MEG will not be considered as data collection techniques for the data pipeline.

Figure 1.

Illustrative Overview of EEG (Gippsland Specialist Clinic, 2026), MEG (Cleveland Clinic, 2023), and EMG (Barrow Neurological Institute, 2026) Measurement Devices

Muscular Activity

Muscular movement is normally controlled by electrochemical signals originating in the brain, driven by sodium ion activity and transmitted through neural pathways to initiate muscle contraction (Loizaga et al., 2023). Since “there is a direct connection between the intensity of the electrochemical signal at the muscle end and the movement’s strength or lack thereof” (Loizaga et al., 2023, p. 4), these electromyography (EMG) signals can be used to detect fatigue (Kyeong & Kim, 2018; Lin et al., 2019).

Obtaining EMG signals in a work environment, however, is intrusive (Cavuoto & Megahed, 2017). This is because EMG requires either inserting needle electrodes into the muscle or placing surface electrodes directly on the skin (Figure 1) (Loizaga et al., 2023). Both methods do not go well together with movement, sweat, or protective clothing. Hence, muscular activity is excluded as a physical fatigue metric, and EMG is not being considered for data collection in the development of this research’s artefact.

Cardiovascular Activity

Cardiovascular activity can also be linked to physical fatigue (Loizaga et al., 2023). Prior studies, including Damit et al., (2017), demonstrate that a substantial increase in heart rate (HR) serves as an

indicator of physical fatigue. Furthermore, Kao & Cornell (2025) suggest heart rate variability (HRV) as a measure for assessing physical fatigue as they found out that “physical fatigue led to significant reductions in HRV” (p. 11).

HR and HRV can be measured using electrocardiography (ECG) or photoplethysmography (PPG) (Loizaga et al., 2023). Both techniques allow for non-intrusive monitoring through wearables (Figure 2) in industrial environments. Thus, cardiovascular activity is identified as a potential physical fatigue metric for this study. Consequentially, both ECG and PPG are considered as potentially viable techniques for data collection in the development of this research’s artefact.

Figure 2.

Illustrative Overview of Single-Lead ECG (Polar Electro, 2026), PPG (Apple Inc., 2026), and IMU (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017) Measurement Devices

Movement Dynamics

Muscular fatigue, along with the associated reduction in strength within specific muscular chains, can result in alterations in movement dynamics (Loizaga et al., 2023). Consequently, a detailed analysis of body-part acceleration can be employed for the assessment of physical fatigue. Prior work has demonstrated that both raw acceleration and derived features are among the strongest predictors of fatigue during physically demanding tasks (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017). Motion-tracking devices such as inertial measurement units (IMUs) (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017) and accelerometers (Cavuoto & Megahed, 2017) can be used to collect this data.

These sensor types (Figure 2) are available in compact wearable formats that can be attached to the body without restricting movement or hindering the operator (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017). Therefore, they enable non-intrusive measurement in industrial settings. Thus, movement dynamics is identified as a potential physical fatigue metric, and IMUs and accelerometers are considered as viable techniques for data collection in the development of this research’s artefact.

Overview of Main Physiological Indicators and Measurements of Physical Fatigue

Type of Measurement	Features	Techniques	Valid	Non-Intrusive	Relevant to Research
Brain	Appearance of ECDs, Reduction of PAF in motor, frontal and/or pre-frontal cortexes	MEG, EEG	Yes	No	No
Muscular	Limited electrochemical signal	EMG	Yes	No	No

Cardiovascular	Significant increase in HR, Significant decrease in HRV	ECG, PPG	Yes	Yes	Yes
Movement Dynamics	Appearance of reduced acceleration	IMU, Accelerometer	Yes	Yes	Yes

Bibliography

- Apple Inc. (2026). Apple Watch Series 11. <https://www.apple.com/apple-watch-series-11/>
- Barrow Neurological Institute. (2026). Electromyography (EMG). <https://www.barrowneuro.org/treatment/electromyography-emg/>
- Cavuoto, L., & Megahed, F. (2017). Understanding Fatigue: Implications for Worker Safety. *Professional Safety*, 62(12), 16–19. https://foundation.assp.org/docs/BPCav_1217z.pdf
- Cleveland Clinic. (2023, March 30). What is magnetoencephalography (MEG)? <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diagnostics/17218-magnetoencephalography-meg>
- Damit, D. N. F. P., Senanayake, S. M. N. A., Malik, O. A., & Tuah, N. J. T. (2017). Neuromuscular Fatigue Analysis of Soldiers Using DWT Based EMG and EEG Data Fusion During Load Carriage. In N. T. Nguyen, S. Tojo, L. M. Nguyen, & B. Trawiński (Eds.), *Intelligent Information and Database Systems Part II* (Vol. 10192, pp. 602–612). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-54430-4>
- Gippsland Specialist Clinic. (2026). EEG. <https://gippslandspecialistclinic.com.au/service/eeg/>
- Kao, P.-C., & Cornell, D. J. (2025). Effects of Induced Physical Fatigue on Heart Rate Variability in Healthy Young Adults. *Sensors*, 25(17), 5572. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25175572>
- Kyeong, S., & Kim, J. (2018). Fatigue characteristics of surface electromyography during walking. 2018 18th International Conference on Control, Automation and Systems (ICCAS), 897–899. <https://doi.org/10.23919/ICCAS.2018.8571979>
- Lin, T.-C., Krishnan, A. U., & Li, Z. (2019). Physical Fatigue Analysis of Assistive Robot Teleoperation via Whole-body Motion Mapping. 2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2240–2245. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS40897.2019.8968544>
- Loizaga, E., Eyam, A. T., Bastida, L., & Lastra, J. I. M. (2023). A Comprehensive Study of Human Factors, Sensory Principles, and Commercial Solutions for Future Human-Centered Working Operations in Industry 5.0. *IEEE Access*, 11, 53806–53829. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3280071>
- Ng, S. C., & Raveendran, P. (2007). EEG Peak Alpha Frequency as an Indicator for Physical Fatigue. In T. Jarm, A. Županič, & P. Kramar (Eds.), *11th Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biomedical Engineering and Computing 2007* (Vol. 16, pp. 517–520). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73044-6_132
- Polar Electro. (2026). Polar H10. Polar België. <https://www.polar.com/be-nl/sensors/h10-heart-rate-sensor>
- Sedighi Maman, Z., Alamdar Yazdi, M. A., Cavuoto, L. A., & Megahed, F. M. (2017). A data-driven approach to modeling physical fatigue in the workplace using wearable sensors. *Applied Ergonomics*, 65, 515–529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2017.02.001>
- Tanaka, M., Ishii, A., & Watanabe, Y. (2013). Neural Correlates of Central Inhibition during Physical Fatigue. *PLoS ONE*, 8(7), e70949. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0070949>